

MODERN FORMS AND METHODS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' ECOLOGICAL CULTURE

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Abstract. *In higher education, an effective system of ecological education and upbringing should be developed, linking students' professional training with the challenges of integrating ecology into scientific and technological progress. Here, an ecologically valuable attitude toward nature, along with practical ecological experience, serves as a key criterion for assessing the effectiveness of ecological education. This article presents an analysis of educational methods for developing students' ecological culture and their possible application in the university educational process.*

Keywords: *ecological education, ecological culture, knowledge, skills, competencies, upbringing, game-based learning, educational activities.*

Introduction

In our country, evaluation of ecology as a multidisciplinary field, scientific essence of ecology, application of parts whose meaning is a product of innovative and creative thinking in education, quality of environmental education and its effectiveness are expanding. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5863 dated October 30, 2019 "On Approval of the Concept of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Period Until 2030" sets the priority task of "Prevention of environmental problems that harm the environment, public health, and gene pool." In the implementation of this task, improving the quality of education and modernizing the teaching methodology based on the selection of educational materials for the formation of environmental education competencies as a result of the scientific imagination of students regarding environmental problems in their activities is one of the urgent problems of today.

The place where a person's umbilical cord blood was shed, where he was born, where he grew up, his homeland, his country, is considered his small homeland. Loving one's country, his homeland is "great love for a small homeland", and being proud of it is fighting for the prosperity, happiness, and peace of the homeland. The word homeland embodies the generous land, the blue sky, the endless fields, gardens, and the precious land in which one lives.

Methodology

Education in general and ecological education in particular, is now considered a crucial factor determining a nation's and a state's well-being, as well as the development of its economy and society. Research on improving the quality of higher education is conducted in several directions. Efforts are being made to reform the entire system of higher education, restructure its framework, update its content, expand the scope of "academic services," and more. The development of a new educational paradigm is closely linked to the growth of the information society. Unlike the traditional paradigm, which focuses on transmitting a set amount of knowledge from one generation to another, the new paradigm aims to cultivate a continuous need for

knowledge acquisition and renewal, skill enhancement, and their transformation into competencies [2].

There is no universally accepted definition of the term "ecological culture." According to N. B. Melnik, "Ecological culture is an aspect of general culture" that "integrates axiological, operational, and semiotic components of human life in the context of their interaction with the natural environment" [5]. The author identifies three spheres of an individual's ecological culture: informational-intellectual (ecological knowledge), emotional-value-based (ecological values and orientations), and activity-volitional (ecological behavior).

E. V. Asafova defines ecological culture as a generalized characteristic of personal qualities that reflects the process and result of shaping an individual's ecological consciousness. It presupposes an inseparable unity between the sum of knowledge about nature, emotional-value-based and sensory attitudes toward it, and the necessary skills, competencies, and needs for interacting with it based on harmonizing relationships in the "nature-human" system. This culture is formed through the integration of three key aspects: ecological consciousness, moral-aesthetic, and practical-activity-based relationships [1].

In higher education, an effective system of ecological education and upbringing should be developed, linking students' professional training with the challenges of integrating ecology into scientific and technological progress. Here, an ecologically valuable attitude toward nature, along with practical ecological experience, serves as a key criterion for assessing the effectiveness of ecological education.

The task of modern education is not only to provide knowledge or turn it into a tool for creative engagement with the world but also to prioritize the preservation and development of students' personal qualities, creativity, intellect, and life-value orientations. The education system today faces the challenge of improving quality. A key direction in achieving this, in light of the state educational standards, is the development of core competencies and interdisciplinary skills, which would enable graduates to work independently, engage in self-education, and realize their full potential—physically, spiritually, and intellectually.

When discussing tools for developing students' ecological culture, it is essential to recognize that everyone enjoys playing—both adults and children—the only difference lies in the subject matter and goals of the game. Games can serve both recreational and educational purposes, including environmental education. Games are a universal means of rekindling interest in exploration and research activities, making them the first step toward cultivating ecological culture.

The Russian physiologist I. P. Pavlov discovered the orienting reflex, also known as the "What is it?" reflex: when a person notices a new object, they involuntarily examine it to understand what it is. Even upon hearing a sound, a person instinctively looks for its source, facilitating the perception of auditory information. Consequently, the highest level of knowledge retention occurs when the instructor's verbal explanations are combined with visual representations during the learning process. Electronic learning tools enhance this process by maximizing the potential of both visual and auditory perception.

Interactive education methods such as training sessions, brainstorming, heuristic discussions, business games, and case studies are also effective in ecological education. Intellectual and situational games, various simulation techniques, theatrical role-playing, and even literary evenings remain relevant. However, due to the high social importance and urgency of ecological issues, the game-based learning format should be further developed by increasing the

number of business games that teach students critical thinking, decision-making, and management approaches to ecological challenges [4].

Results and discussion

Ecology as a science is only beginning to gain widespread popularity in our country. However, the growing interest in complex ecological problems serves as a stimulus for integrating this field into higher education institutions. Many universities have successfully implemented the "scientific dialogue" method—a debate between two "scientists" (students acting as scholars) on an ecological topic. These scholars present different, sometimes completely opposing, perspectives, including deliberately weak arguments. Another method, "scientific debates," involves competitions between two or more teams on given topics. By employing such tools and demonstrating that science can be accessible and engaging, it is possible to foster greater interest in ecology, leading to a deeper understanding of environmental issues [6].

Using drawings, diagrams, and graphs is another crucial aspect of analyzing information. Graphical representation allows for the clear demonstration of ecological problems in a given region, among other applications. For example:

Conclusion

The rapid advancement of science and technology and the integration of scientific methods into all aspects of human activity have necessitated the development of students' creative and cognitive abilities. The key indicator of educational effectiveness is no longer merely the sum of subject-specific knowledge acquired by students, but rather their ability to independently obtain and apply new knowledge throughout their academic and professional lives.

Educational and upbringing activities should primarily aim at shaping firm convictions that guide an individual's behavior. Convictions determine people's value orientations and attitudes toward nature, influencing their conscious and responsible engagement with the environment. A well-developed system of ecological beliefs and values can serve as an indicator of high ecological

culture among students. High ecological awareness, in turn, stimulates intellectual curiosity and motivates individuals to acquire and apply new ecological knowledge.

In the 21st century, fostering a strong orientation toward ecologically significant values is crucial not only for an individual's successful life but also for preserving national culture. The ability to interact effectively with others and the natural world is one of the fundamental conditions for a well-rounded and fulfilling personal life [3].

Thus, at the current stage of university education reform, developing students' ecological culture should be seen as an essential component of their successful self-realization, increasing their societal demand and preparing them for a way of life in harmony with nature.

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